

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

RECETOX, Faculty of Science, Masaryk University, Czech Republic

Title: SOP for pre-acquisition normalisation of urine via specific gravity

Date: 19.05.2020

Version: version 1

Authors: Elliott J. Price

Summary

Compared to other human matrices, urine is advantageous because it can be easily collected in large volumes, non-invasively. However, intra-and inter-individual urine volume and solute concentration varies greatly (>15-fold) in relation to dietary, hormonal, physiological and behavioural factors. This high variation biases full-scan mass spectrometry (MS) profiling methods due to different urine concentrations analysed. As such, to enable generation of comparative data requires pre-acquisition normalisation i.e. before MS analysis. Described here is specific gravity normalisation, which has been favoured because it is independent of other chemical measures (e.g. creatinine) and easy for routine measurement (compared to osmolality).

Preparation

Safety information

- Urine is classified as a potentially biohazardous material & thus all items in contact (e.g. pipette tips, vials) should be disposed of appropriately.

Equipment

- 1 uL, 10 uL, 100 uL, 200 uL & 1 mL pipettes
- Handheld digital refractometer for urine specific gravity (range 1.0000-1.0600, accuracy +/- 0.001)
- Storage boxes and racks for tubes / vials (size dependent on volumes needed)
 - Typically only need for 2 mL vials / tubes
- Mini vortex

Consumables & glassware

- Vials / tubes (size dependent on volumes needed) and caps
 - Typically only need 2 mL glass vials for samples
- Labels for tubes / vials
- Paper towel
- 2 uL, 10 uL, 200 uL & 1 mL tips

Reagents

- Fresh / thawed urine
 - Keep freeze-thaw cycles to a minimum, ideally only once.
 - Thaw urine at room temperature directly prior to analysis & store on ice.
- Fresh milliQ water at room temperature
- Liquid washing soap solution

Procedure

Specific gravity measurement

1. Blank refractometer using 300 uL milliQ water.
2. Wipe refractometer with paper towel until dry.
3. Add 300 uL milliQ and ensure value of 1.000
4. Wipe refractometer with paper towel until dry.
5. Vortex urine sample, pipette 300 uL onto refractometer & wait until stabilised temperature.
 - If sample volume is limited can reduce to 100 uL.
 - If sample volume is severely limited can pipette urine off refractometer into clean vial. If doing so, also do same for milliQ water to use as contamination blank.
6. Record specific gravity (SG) of first sample (typical range 1.002-1.035).
7. Wipe dry refractometer, add 300 uL milliQ to wash and wipe dry again.
8. Measure and record SG of subsequent samples, following step 7 between each sample.
 - Once finished wash refractometer with soap and warm water, then rinse in milliQ water.

Normalisation

9. Dilute samples to 1mL into fresh, labelled vial using milliQ water.
 - To achieve uniform specific gravity of 1.002, using the following equation:

$$\text{A) Volume urine (uL)} = 1000 * [(1.0020-1)/ SG_{\text{Urine}}-1]]$$

$$\text{B) Volume milliQ (uL)} = 1000 - \text{volume urine (uL) calculated in A}$$

- If sample volume is severely limited, can dilute samples to 100 uL, via:

$$\text{C) Volume urine (uL)} = 100 * [(1.0020-1)/ SG_{\text{Urine}}-1]]$$

$$\text{D) Volume milliQ (uL)} = 100 - \text{volume urine (uL) calculated in C}$$

10. Vortex samples, store on ice and proceed with subsequent analysis.